

A Phenomenological Investigation of Teachers' Understanding of the Ethnomathematics Approach

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ABSTRACT

Ethnomathematics is an emerging field investigating different cultures and communities' mathematical practices and systems. It is a culturally responsive approach to teaching mathematics that aims to incorporate cultural diversity into the teaching and learning of mathematics. Despite the positive impact on students' learning and retention rates, the educational aspect of this phenomenon still needs to be explored, necessitating the investigation and comprehensive understanding of its implications. The study used a phenomenological research design to explore the lived experiences of mathematics teachers integrating cultural context into their lessons. Three teachers from Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, were selected using maximum variation purposive sampling to provide diverse perspectives on the ethnomathematics approach. Data was collected through in-depth, semi-structured interviews, focusing on teachers' experiences and insights regarding incorporating cultural elements in mathematics education. Participants viewed the ethnomathematics approach as deeply connecting mathematics and culture, implementing it through anthropological, student-centered, and interdisciplinary methods. They agreed that integrating culture in mathematics is crucial for an inclusive curriculum and developing 21st-century skills, though some unique ideas came from individual participants. These findings have enriched the body of knowledge regarding the educational dimension of ethnomathematics. The researchers recommend that teachers interested in applying the ethnomathematics approach should leverage students' cultural backgrounds, integrate these perspectives into other subjects, and expose students to diverse mathematical practices from various cultures. Such strategies can support student-centered learning, promote a more inclusive curriculum, and foster the development of 21st-century skills.

Keywords: *Ethnomathematics Approach, Exploratory Study, Mathematics Education*

INTRODUCTION

Ethnomathematics is a field of study that examines the connections between mathematics and culture. It focuses on how mathematics is used and understood in different cultures worldwide and how cultural perspectives and practices influence mathematical concepts and processes (Rosa & Gavarrete, 2017). It can enhance mathematics education by recognizing cultural relevance and incorporating culturally relevant material into the mathematical curriculum. (Rosa & Orey, 2016).

Ethnomathematics is relevant in modern classrooms because it recognizes that mathematics is not just a set of abstract concepts and procedures but is also influenced by culture and history (Rosa & Gavarrete, 2017). One promising approach in mathematics education emphasizes building upon students' knowledge and background (D'Ambrosio, 2001). This approach recognizes a student's environment's significant role in shaping their learning. It considers the content available in their surroundings and the learning methods they have encountered. Furthermore, it acknowledges the impact of past and present experiences within a student's immediate environment. This focus on the learner's context can be translated into practical teaching methods, such as hands-on activities. It helps students see the connection between mathematics and their everyday lives and encourages them to explore different cultures' mathematical practices and knowledge. (Shirley, 2015; Rosa & Orey, 2016; Rosa & Gavarrete, 2017).

The study anchors on ethnomathematics' educational aspect, centered on finding ways to incorporate ethnomathematical ideas into mathematics curriculum in content and methods (Ascher & D'Ambrosio, 1994). This aspect is evident in the K to 12 Mathematics Curriculum Guide of the Philippines, which advocates that the various contexts of Filipino students be taken into account when teaching mathematics (Department of Education, 2013). Several studies in this aspect focused on investigating how ethnomathematics improves the quality of mathematics education (Albuero, 2019).

Indonesia provides a particularly fertile ground for exploring ethnomathematics, with abundant relevant studies (Mania & Alam, 2021). This cultural context allows students to connect mathematical concepts to their heritage, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation. The Indonesian National Curriculum further supports this approach by emphasizing cultural relevance in education. Furthermore, the average ability of mathematical comprehension students taught using the ethnomathematics approach was higher than those taught using the conventional learning approach (Widada et al., 2019), similar to the study of Kusuma et al. (2019). Moreover, the probing prompting based on the ethnomathematics learning model influences the students' mathematical communication skills (Hartinah et al., 2019). Moreover, students may be able to simplify the concept of function to make it more meaningful with an ethnomathematics approach (Herawaty et al., 2020).

However, in the Philippines, most of the studies are anchored on the anthropological aspect of ethnomathematics, which is focused on investigating the mathematical ideas embedded in cultural practices and traditions. Literature on the educational aspect of ethnomathematics is limited but expanding. However, only some empirical studies (Anchor et al., 2009; Kurumeh et al., 2012; Aktuna, 2013) show that including ethnomathematics in math curricula positively impacts students' learning and retention rates.

With the studies mentioned above, it is evident that integrating culture into mathematics education improves the quality of mathematics education despite the ethnocentric view that mathematics is a universally objective and culture-free subject, as Wiest (2001) pointed out. This current study addressed the limited extant literature on the educational aspect of ethnomathematics in the Philippines as an instructional approach. The findings of this study will provide mathematics teachers with ways to incorporate culture in teaching mathematics and add to the existing body of knowledge on ethnomathematics.

The study explores the mathematics teachers' understanding of ethnomathematics in the classroom regarding its definition, implementation, and importance through an in-depth individual (IDI) interview. IDI interview is used since it is one of the most powerful tools for exploring topics in-depth (Fontana & Frey, 2000). Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the teachers' understanding of ethnomathematics in the classroom?
2. How do teachers incorporate culture in the teaching of mathematics?
3. Why is using culture essential to making mathematics meaningful for the students?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized a phenomenological research design, which involves gaining an in-depth understanding of the lived experiences of the research participants through interviews (Wilson, 2015), focusing on their perceptions and experiences. The study explored the participants' experiences with the ethnomathematics approach in their classroom.

Participant of the Study

The study used a non-probability criterion sampling (Cohen & Crabtree, 2006), specifically maximum variation purposive sampling (Rai & Thapa, 2015) to identify participants. The criterion for selecting the participants was primarily a mathematics teacher, handling mathematics throughout any grade level and incorporating culture with the mathematics lesson in any modality. Maximum variation purposive sampling was employed to gain more significant insights into a phenomenon by looking at it from all angles, which can often aid the researcher in identifying common patterns apparent throughout the sample (Rai & Thapa, 2015).

In addition, Creswell (2007) suggested a sample size of 3 to 5 participants for a qualitative inquiry and employed maximum variation as a sampling strategy. With this, data source triangulation was utilized, which entails gathering information from different types of people to obtain multiple viewpoints and validate data (Carter et al., 2014). In this current study, the researchers interviewed three (3) teachers who voluntarily participated in the data collection process. All participants are mathematics teachers who agreed to provide their experiences and narratives in teaching mathematical concepts through cultural integration with the researchers.

The research locale is Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, known for its diverse indigenous cultures, which may have unique perspectives and practices on mathematics (National Government Portal, 2023). Ethnomathematics aims to explore the cultural aspects of mathematics, and Malaybalay City could provide a rich source of knowledge in this regard. Two participants are from a private institution, and one is from a public institution. Each participant completed a personal information

form containing their demographic profile, as shown in Table 1. The researchers assigned pseudonyms to the three (3) participants to protect their identity while maintaining the humanness of their accounts and experiences. The researchers selected participants who differ significantly in their years of teaching experience, given the vast evidence in the existing literature of the relationship between teaching experience, teacher effectiveness, and quality of teaching.

Table 1.
Demographic profile of the participants

Participant	Gender	Age	Year Teaching	Grade Level	Educational Attainment
MT-1	Female	50	29	7	Master's Degree
MT-2	Male	25	5	9 & 11	Baccalaureate Degree
MT-3	Female	24	1	10 & 11	Baccalaureate Degree

Data Collection

The researchers used a researcher-made questionnaire to gather relevant information regarding the study. Experts validated the content and structure, gauging the teachers' application of cultural context into their mathematics lessons, considering the teachers' definition of Ethnomathematics, incorporation of the approach, and the importance of integrating culture with mathematics lessons.

Data collection employed in-depth, semi-structured, face-to-face interviews (Cresswell, 2002). These individual interviews were conducted at a location chosen by each participant to ensure a comfortable and private environment. This approach fostered open and honest responses, allowing participants to freely share their perspectives, experiences, and insights regarding the use of cultural context within mathematics lessons by their teachers. The language used in the data gathering was English. Moreover, the study employed an exploratory interview method as an appropriate research process within the real-life context that precludes further research studies (Yin, 2014).

The study focused on exploring the understanding of the mathematics teachers of the ethnomathematics approach; the study clustered the interview questions into three distinct but interrelated categories to help the first step of qualitative content analysis. The first section of the interview explored the category of each participant's definition of the ethnomathematics approach from their personal opinions. The second interview category explores the participant's incorporation of culture in mathematics teaching. Moreover, the third interview category explores the importance of making mathematics meaningful for students. At the end of the interview, the researchers explicitly checked with each participant to determine if they were satisfied with their responses or needed to add anything to their narratives.

The researcher recorded the individual interview sessions with the participants. The interview schedules took between 53 to 87 minutes to complete. The researchers implemented the Data Privacy Act (2012) provision in the data gathering process. This study obtained written consent from each participant, allowing them to record the interview session on an audio recorder. To ensure the study's trustworthiness, the researchers transcribed the interviews into printed transcripts, and each participant had the opportunity to read through their interview transcripts, discuss any discrepancies with the researcher, and approve the accuracy of the transcript from their perspective.

Data Analysis

Qualitative content analysis was employed to analyze the interview transcripts. This method involves systematically coding and identifying themes or patterns within the textual data to gain a subjective understanding of its content. Conventional content analysis was chosen explicitly as the existing research on using cultural context in mathematics lessons by teachers might need to be expanded (Hsieh & Shannon, 2005). This approach allows for the emergence of new themes from the data itself. This study needs more extant literature on the educational aspect of Ethnomathematics in the Philippines, specifically regarding an instructional approach.

The data analysis was conducted following the suggested steps of Hsieh and Shannon (2005) in conducting conventional content analysis. First, the researchers read all data repeatedly over two weeks to achieve immersion and obtain a sense of the whole (Tesch, 1990) before the coding process. By doing this, the study's trustworthiness was established (Nowell et al., 2017). Second, the researcher assumed the role of coder and conducted a meticulous examination of the interview transcripts. The coding involved a close reading, word-by-word, to identify and extract codes. These codes represent significant phrases or terminology within the text that capture vital concepts or critical ideas expressed by the participants (Morgan, 1993; Miles & Huberman, 1994; Morse & Field, 1995). At this stage, the researcher-coder used NVIVO 14, a qualitative data analysis software, which is a handy tool for analyzing and interpreting semi-structured interviews (Lopezosa, 2020).

The "*Code In Vivo*" feature was used after highlighting the exact words from the interview transcripts that help answer the research questions of this current study. Through this, the researcher-coder allowed the codes to flow from the data. Next, the researcher-coder sorts the codes into categories based on how different codes are related and linked. Most of the codes were combined during this stage. To establish trustworthiness in the study, the researcher-coder used Microsoft Word to keep detailed notes about the development and hierarchies of concepts and themes (Nowell et al., 2017). These notes were sent to the other research team members for feedback. Finally, the researcher-coder incorporated the feedback and used the emergent categories to organize codes into meaningful themes (Coffey & Atkinson, 1996; Patton, 2002). At this stage, the researchers reached a consensus on themes, which also helped establish trustworthiness in the study (Nowell et al., 2017).

Limitation of the Study

The limitation of this study is found in the limited data from teachers since the only variation considered in the sampling procedure was the number of years of teaching. Consequently, this study cannot comprehensively understand the ethnomathematics approach. Therefore, future research can further explore the ethnomathematics approach by involving mathematics teachers with differences in cultural experience or ethnicity, and students as participants can be further examined.

Trustworthiness of the Study

The researchers know that the ethnomathematics approach is about integrating culture into teaching mathematics, but they have yet to learn how this could be done and its importance in making mathematics more meaningful to students. Thus, it can be said that the data analysis results

were data-driven and were free from researchers' preconceived notions. Moreover, following the recommendations of Nowell et al. (2000), the study's trustworthiness was enhanced in three ways. First, the researchers read all data repeatedly over two weeks to achieve immersion and obtain a sense of the whole (Tesch, 1990) before the coding process. Second, the researcher-coder used Microsoft Word to document all procedures, such as keeping detailed notes about development and hierarchies of concepts and themes. These were sent to the other research team members for feedback. Lastly, the researcher-coder incorporated the feedback and used the emergent categories to organize codes into meaningful themes (Coffey & Atkinson, 1996; Patton, 2002). At this stage, the researchers finalized the names of the codes and reached a consensus on themes.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to strict ethical guidelines throughout the research process. Participants were fully informed about the study's objectives and their involvement through a detailed information sheet. Those deemed competent to provide consent must sign an informed consent form before the interview. This form clearly outlined their right to participate voluntarily and to withdraw from the study at any point, even after signing. To ensure anonymity and confidentiality, participant names and identities were not linked to any data collected, analyzed, or reported in the study findings. Interviews were conducted individually in private settings, with only the researcher accessing recordings that could identify participants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the data analysis, the researchers identified one (1) emerging theme in the teachers' definition of ethnomathematics in the classroom. The ethnomathematics approach is a way of understanding mathematics through culture because they are intertwined. Moreover, there were four (4) emerging themes on how mathematics teachers incorporate culture in teaching mathematics. The four themes are anthropological, experience-based, interdisciplinary, and student-centered. In addition, there were two (2) emerging themes on the importance of using culture: towards curriculum and culture.

Teachers' Understanding Regarding Ethnomathematics in the Classroom

Based on the participant's responses, the ethnomathematics approach is a way of understanding mathematics through culture because they are intertwined. It is the label assigned to describe the definition of the participants for ethnomathematics. The mathematics teachers acknowledged that culture can be integrated into teaching mathematics, and it can help students understand mathematics. This insight contrasts the ethnocentric view that mathematics is a universally objective and culture-free subject, as pointed out by Wiest (2001). FMT-1 shared that the integration can be done by relating mathematical concepts to students' cultural experiences, traditional cultural symbols, patterns, crafts, images, and designs.

The result was further reaffirmed when MMT-2 mentioned cultural practices such as storytelling, music, dance, art, games, and puzzles. In addition, FMT-3 shared the use of traditional cooking and food preparation methods. This insight of the participants resulted when they acknowledged that mathematical concepts intertwined with culture, which supports the idea that math is everywhere in the study of Díez-Palomar et al. (2007) when students were working on projects that connected mathematics to their lives. This experience reveals the connections

between mathematics and everyday life, which are revealed while emphasizing culture, language, and conversation among math students.

Teachers' incorporation of culture in Teaching Mathematics

The most common theme to emerge from the participants' ways of implementing the ethnomathematics approach was the anthropological aspect of mathematics. It is focused on investigating the mathematical ideas embedded in cultural practices and traditions. Based on the participants' responses, anthropological is the label assigned when they expose students to various math practices from different cultures, let students engage with diverse mathematical traditions and practices, and explore the mathematical concepts of cultural practices to understand them better. The participants emphasized culture more than mathematical concepts, which their way of defining the ethnomathematics approach can explain – mathematics is intertwined with culture.

“Students can explore the mathematics behind traditional cultural practices such as weaving, pottery, or architecture to gain a deeper understanding of the cultural significance of these practices.” (FMT-1)

“Ahh, I guess through the study and analysis of mathematical practices in different cultures.” (MMT-2)

“Hmm, for me, I use it to teach students about the mathematical principles behind traditional cooking and food preparation methods.” (FMT-3)

Using ethnomathematics becomes anthropological because it involves the study of the mathematical practices and concepts of different cultural groups. In this way, it helps to reveal mathematics' cultural, social, and historical dimensions and how it is intertwined with other aspects of people's lives (Herawaty et al., 2020). Applying the ethnomathematics approach is consistent with how the participants defined it. This present study is anchored on the educational aspect of ethnomathematics. However, seeing that the anthropological aspect was utilized, this can be seen as proof that anthropological and pedagogical aspects are related, although most studies in this area were conducted as independent research projects. (Albuero, 2019).

The participants shared some characteristics of student-centered learning when implementing an ethnomathematics approach in the classroom. They cited the teaching of mathematics concepts by relating them to students' cultural backgrounds and engaging the students. Use of Students' Cultural Background. Student-centered learning is a model in which students are placed at the core of the learning process, and students' needs, opinions, backgrounds, and goals are acknowledged and incorporated within the learning environment (Thamraksa, 2003). In implementing the ethnomathematics approach, participants used students' cultural backgrounds (Mosimege & Egara, 2022).

FMT-1 stressed teaching mathematics by relating the concepts to students' own cultural experiences. Moreover, MMT -2 emphasized that the learning environment is more equitable when the experiences of students from diverse backgrounds are acknowledged and valued. These align with Suharta et al.'s (2021) findings, and Suharta et al. (2017) findings that ethnomathematics-based mathematics learning using problems close to student life is student-centered learning. In addition, FMT-1 even said that students can do this independently by understanding the mathematical practices of different cultures and relating them to their own experiences.

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This is in adherence to Serin (2018) regarding student-centered instruction, which allows students to construct their understandings using their experiences and actions. Meanwhile, for FMT-3, there was no explicit mention of using students' cultural backgrounds. However, it talked about creating effective lesson plans when employing an ethnomathematics approach that addresses the diverse learning needs of the students.

The implementation of the ethnomathematics approach in this study presented that it can support student-centered learning, taking into account the attempts for educational reform or the move from teacher-centered learning to student-centered learning and engaging the students. This category was assigned to the participants' use of culture to engage the students in the classroom. One of the characteristics of student-centered learning is that the students are active participants in the learning process (Thamraksa, 2003). MMT-2 specifically mentioned collaborative learning, where students share their knowledge and cultural experiences.

The focus on collaboration aligns well with the findings, as this approach fosters student engagement. Collaborative learning has become a powerful tool for promoting human interaction in the 21st century, making it a promising pedagogical trend (Laal & Ghodsi, 2012). Another type of engagement is with the mathematical content shared by FMT-3, which is done by incorporating real-world contexts and cultural perspectives. The engagement happened because the use of culture fueled students' curiosity. This can be termed curiosity-driven engagement (Wu et al., 2018). For FMT-1, to cultivate a sense of curiosity, students were engaged with diverse mathematical traditions and practices. One particular example used by FMT-1 was showcasing the mathematical contributions of historically marginalized groups. Another way of engaging the students was to let them play traditional games and puzzles from different cultures.

“For me, I utilize math games and puzzles from different cultures because when I was young, we kept on playing games with my friends. And I thought that games are also useful in learning that’s why I use games and puzzles.” (MMT-2)

MMT-2, being a teacher, used his experiences in implementing the ethnomathematics approach and remarked that it was fun. Since engagement includes constructs such as enjoyment and fun with game activities (Pettit, 2015), the students of MMT-2 were indeed engaged. These results agree with (Mania & Alam, 2021) that teaching math through ethnomathematics is exciting and capable of presenting context and engagement.

The participants integrate knowledge from other disciplines to let students understand the mathematical concepts while employing an ethnomathematics approach. Ethnomathematics is an interdisciplinary field that attempts to illuminate the various ways mathematics and culture are related (Bender & Beller, 2011). The participants mentioned that disciplines such as architecture, music, culinary arts, engineering, and other fields had cultural aspects integrated into teaching mathematics.

“I used it to help students understand the complex geometric patterns found in Islamic art, such as those seen in mosques and other buildings.” (FMT-1)

“Students can explore the mathematics behind traditional cultural practices such as weaving, pottery, or architecture to gain a deeper understanding of the cultural significance of these practices.” (FMT-1)

“Ethnomathematics approach focuses on the integration of mathematical concepts with cultural practices, such as storytelling, music, dance, and art.” (MMT-2)

“It recognizes that mathematical concepts and techniques can be found in various cultural artifacts, such as music, art, and architecture.” (FMT-3)

Moreover, FMT-3 also integrated the teaching of mathematics with the other subjects of the students.

“For me, I use it to teach students about the mathematical principles behind traditional cooking and food preparation methods since measurements, ratios, and patterns are included. In TLE subject, in the part where they do cooking, I work along with the lesson from the other class.” (FMT-3)

Given that ethnomathematics is an interdisciplinary field, it is easy to integrate the teaching of mathematics using an ethnomathematics approach with the other subjects of the students.

Importance of Using Culture for Making Mathematics Meaningful for Students

The ethnomathematics approach offers a more inclusive curriculum. The participants' most cited words when mentioning inclusive curriculum were respect and appreciation. The participants focused on respect and appreciation toward students with diverse cultural backgrounds and other cultures.

“Ethnomathematics approach helps to create learning environments that are more welcoming and respectful of all students regardless of their cultural backgrounds.” (FMT-1)

“...recognizing and respecting the mathematical knowledge and practices of all students regardless of their cultural background.” (MMT-2)

“Ethnomathematics approach can help to challenge stereotypes and biases about different cultures and their mathematical practices, encouraging respect and appreciation for those practices.” (FMT-3)

Diversity is one essential component that needs to be infused into the syllabus to promote an inclusive learning environment, which includes race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, age, religious affiliation, disability status, social class, culture, and other identities associated with sociocultural diversity. Ways how the participants in this study addressed diversity in the classroom were mentioned above in the “engaging the students” category, which is consistent with the specific outcomes that appear to align with equity, diversity, and inclusion (EDI) ideology, such as building and enhancing interpersonal relationships, interacting effectively with others, and enhancing teamwork capacity (Fuentes et al., 2021).

Other than this, FMT-1 also highlighted that the ethnomathematics approach would connect mathematics and students' everyday lives.

“The approach positively impacts the teaching and learning of mathematics by offering a more inclusive and culturally responsive curriculum that connects students to their cultural heritage and everyday lives.” (FMT-1)

“The approach would make math lessons more culturally relevant to students which would help them connect with the subject matter and see its applications in their daily lives.” (FMT-1)

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This statement is consistent with meaningful learning, which occurs when humans relate new concepts to pre-existing familiar concepts (Vallori, 2014). One is the culture and environment of everyday students that are integrated into the learning process (Ramadhanti, 2019).

The Ethnomathematics approach fosters 21st-century skills. Based on the participant's responses, the ethnomathematics approach helps develop 21st-century skills such as creativity, critical thinking, problem-solving, collaboration (Partnership21, 2008), and curiosity (Wagner, 2008).

"Considering the cultural context of mathematics fosters creativity." (FMT-1)

"It encourages critical thinking by examining the cultural biases that are inherent in many mathematical systems." (MMT-2)

"Ethnomathematics approach promotes the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills through the exploration of different cultural contexts. It enables learners to appreciate the diversity of mathematical thinking and encourages them to develop creative ways of solving problems." (FMT-3)

"It will encourage students to engage with mathematical content and fuel their curiosity to learn more." (FMT-3)

This was possible because the participants highlighted student-centered learning by employing an ethnomathematics approach in the classroom, which can lead to increased student learning and engagement (Medeiros et al., 2018). Students had curiosity-driven engagement because the participants integrated culture into teaching mathematics. This could lead to meaningful learning and provide students with ways to achieve 21st-century skills (Kolb, 2014).

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study revealed that the understanding of the mathematics teachers of the ethnomathematics approach in the classroom in terms of its definition, implementation, and importance were aligned. Also, their responses converged, but a few ideas only came from one participant. They acknowledged the relatedness of mathematics and culture, which is evident in using the anthropological aspect and interdisciplinary field of ethnomathematics when integrating culture in teaching mathematics. They even supported the relatedness of anthropological and educational aspects of ethnomathematics. Additionally, they extensively used the students' cultural background, which supported student-centered learning, led to a more inclusive curriculum, and assisted in developing 21st-century skills. Moreover, these made the learning of the students meaningful.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The study highlights the importance of incorporating an ethnomathematics approach in teaching mathematics. However, due to the limitation of the study and based on the findings presented above, this study recommends that teachers who are interested in applying the ethnomathematics approach utilize the students' cultural background, integrate it to students' other subjects, and expose students to a wide variety of math practices from different cultures as these can support student-centered learning, lead to a more inclusive curriculum, and assist in the development of 21st-century skills. Future researchers could investigate the relationship between

knowledge of ethnomathematics and effective mathematical instruction in classrooms and design further studies to determine the effectiveness of ethnomathematics education in enhancing students' mathematical performance and attitudes. Moreover, further research could be conducted to explore the impact of ethnomathematics on students' learning outcomes and attitudes toward mathematics. Such studies will help identify gaps and improve the approach.

REFERENCE

- Alburo, F. G. (2019). *Development and Evaluation Of Ethnomathematically-Enriched Learning Material (EELM): A Cabadbaranon ' Experience*. June, 0–9.
- Anchor, E., Imoko, B. and Uloko, E. (2009). Effect Of Ethnomathematics Teaching Approach on Senior Secondary Students' Achievement and Retention in Locus. *Educational Research and Review*, 4(8): 385-390.
- Bender, A., & Beller, S. (2011). *Numerical Cognition and Ethnomathematics*. In Wiley-Blackwell eBooks (pp. 270–289). <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781444394931.ch15>
- Brandt, A. and Chernoff, E.J. (2015) The Importance of Ethnomathematics in the Math Class. *Ohio Journal of School Mathematics*, 2015(71): 31-36
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006), “Using thematic analysis in psychology”, *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2): 77-101.
- Carter, N., Bryant-Lukosius, D., DiCenso, A., Blythe, J., & Neville, A. J. (2014). The Use of Triangulation in Qualitative Research. *Oncology Nursing Forum*, 41(5):545–547. <https://doi.org/10.1188/14.onf.545-547>
- Coffey, A., & Atkinson, P. (1996). *Making sense of qualitative data: Complementary research strategies*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Cohen D. and Crabtree B. (2006). *Qualitative Research Guidelines Project*. <http://www.qualres.org/HomeCrit-3814.html>
- Creswell, J.W. (2002), *Educational Research: Planning, Conducting, and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research*, Merrill Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, NJ.
- Creswell, J. W. (2007). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches* (2nd ed.). Sage Publications, Inc.
- Data Privacy Act, RA § 10173 (2012). <https://officialgazette.gov.ph/images/uploads/20160825-IRR-RA-10173-data-privacy.pdf>
- Department of Education. (2013). *K to 12 Mathematics Curriculum Guide. Pasig City: Department of Education*.
- Díez-Palomar, J., Simic, K., & Varley, M. (2007). Math is everywhere”: Connecting mathematics to students’ lives. *Journal of Mathematics and Culture*, 1(2): 20-36
- D’Ambrosio, U. (2016). *An Overview of the History of Ethnomathematics*. In: *Current and Future Perspectives of Ethnomathematics as a Program*. ICME-13 Topical Surveys. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-30120-4_2
- Fuentes, M. A., Zelaya, D. G., & Madsen, J. W. (2021). Rethinking the Course Syllabus: Considerations for Promoting Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion. *Teaching of Psychology*, 48(1):69-79.
- Hartinah, S., Suherman, S., Syazali, M., Efendi, H., Junaidi, R., Jermsittiparsert, K., & Umam, R. (2019). Probing-prompting based on ethnomathematics learning model: The effect on mathematical communication skills. *Journal for the Education of Gifted Young Scientists*, 7(4), 799–814. <https://doi.org/10.17478/jegys.574275>
- Herawaty, D., Widada, W., Adhitya, A., Sari, R. D. W., Novianita, L., & Falaq Dwi Anggoro, A. (2020). Students’ ability to simplify the concept of function through realistic mathematics learning with the ethnomathematics approach. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1470(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1470/1/012031>
- Hsieh H.F. & Shannon S.E. (2005). Three approaches to qualitative content analysis. *Qual Health Res*. 15(9):1277-88. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049732305276687>.
- Kolb, D. A. (2014). *Experiential Learning: Experience as The Source of Learning and Development*. FT press.

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- Kurumeh, M. S., Onah, F. O., & Mohammed, A. S. (2012). Improving students' retention in junior secondary school statistics using the ethnomathematics teaching approach in Obi and Oju Local Government Areas of Benue State, Nigeria. *Greener Journal of Educational Research*, 2(3), 54-62.
- Kusuma, D. A., Suryadi, D., & Dahlan, J. A. (2019). Improving external mathematical connections and students' activity using ethnomathematics. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1157(3). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1157/3/032120>
- Laal, M., & Ghodsi, S. M. (2012). Benefits of collaborative learning. *Procedia-social and behavioral sciences*, 31:486-490.
- Lopezosa, C. (2020). *Entrevistas semiestructuradas con NVivo: pasos para un análisis cualitativo eficaz*. Lopezosa C, Díaz-Noci J, Codina L, editores *Methodos Anuario de Métodos de Investigación en Comunicación Social*, 1. Barcelona: Universitat Pompeu Fabra; 88-97.
- Mania, S., & Alam, S. (2021). Teachers' perception toward the use of ethnomathematics approach in teaching math. *International Journal of Education in Mathematics, Science and Technology*, 9(2): 282–298. <https://doi.org/10.46328/IJEMST.1551>
- Medeiros, F., Santos, A., Júnior, J. R., & Paz, A. (2018). 21st century skills development in Project-Based Learning at Federal Network of Technological Education Institutes. In *INTED2018 Proceedings* (pp. 9447-9453). IATED.
- Miles, M. B., & Huberman, A. M. (1994). *Qualitative data analysis: An expanded sourcebook*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Morgan, D. L. (1993). Qualitative Content Analysis: A Guide to Paths Not Taken. *Qualitative Health Research*, 3:112-121.
- Morse, J. M., & Field, P. A. (1995). *Qualitative research methods for health professionals* (2nd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Mosimege, M. D., & Egara, F. O. (2022). Perception and perspective of teachers towards the usage of ethnomathematics approach in mathematics teaching and learning. *Multicultural Education*, 8(3): 288-298.
- National Government Portal (2023). *City of Malaybalay – Spatial Demography*. <https://malaybalaycity.gov.ph/spatial-demography/>
- Nowell, L. S., Norris, J. M., White, D. E., & Moules, N. J. (2017). Thematic Analysis: Striving to Meet the Trustworthiness Criteria. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 16(1):1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406917733847>
- Partnership 21. *21st Century Skills, Education, and Competitiveness*. (Tucson: Partnership for 21st century, 2008), retrieved at www.p21.org/storage/documents/21_century_skills_educations_and_competitiveness_guide.pdf
- Patton, M. Q. (2002). *Qualitative research and evaluation methods*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Pettit, R. K., McCoy, L., Kinney, M. and Schwartz, F. N (2015). Student perceptions of gamified audience response system interactions in large group lectures and via lecture capture technology. *BMC medical education*, 15, 1(92).
- Rai, N., & Thapa, B. (2015). A study on purposive sampling method in research. *Kathmandu: Kathmandu School of Law*, 5.
- Ramadhanti, D. (2019). The Joli-Joli's Game in The Learning Writing Poetry: A Culturally Responsive Meaningful Learning Model. *ISLLAC: Journal of Intensive Studies on Language, Literature, Art, and Culture*, 3(1): 26-35
- Rosa, M. and Gavarrete, M.E. (2017). *An Ethnomathematics Overview: An Introduction*. In: Rosa, M., Shirley, L., Gavarrete, M., Alanguí, W. (eds) *Ethnomathematics and its Diverse Approaches for Mathematics Education*. ICME-13 Monographs. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-59220-6_1
- Rosa, M. and Orey, D.C. (2016). *State of the Art in Ethnomathematics*. In: *Current and Future Perspectives of Ethnomathematics as a Program*. ICME-13 Topical Surveys. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-30120-4_3

- Serin, H. (2018). A Comparison of Teacher-Centered and Student-Centered Approaches in Educational Settings. *International Journal of Social Sciences & Educational Studies*, 5(1): 164-167.
- Shirley, L. (2015). Mathematics of students' culture: A goal of localized ethnomathematics. *Revista Latinoamericana de Etnomatemática*, 8(2), 316–325. <https://revista.etnomatematica.org/index.php/RevLatEm/article/view/191>
- Shirley, L., and Palhares, P. (2016). *Ethnomathematics and its diverse pedagogical approaches*. In M. Rosa, U. D'Ambrosio, D. C. Orey, L. Shirley, W. V. Alangui, P. Palhares, & M. E. Gavarrete (Eds.), *Current and future perspectives of ethnomathematics as a program* (pp. 13–17). ICME13 Topical Surveys. London, England: SpringerOpen.
- Suharta, I. G. P., Parwati, N. N., & Pujawan, I. G. N. (2021, July). Integration of Ethnomathematics in Learning Geometry Transformation. In *5th Asian Education Symposium 2020 (AES 2020)* (pp. 107-110). Atlantis Press.
- Suharta, I. G. P., Sudiarta, I. G. P., & Astawa, I. W. P. (2017). Ethnomathematics of Balinese traditional houses. *International Research Journal of Engineering, IT and Scientific Research*, 3(4): 47-56.
- Tesch, R. (1990). *Qualitative research: Analysis types and software tools*. Bristol, PA: Falmer.
- Thamraksa, C. (2003). Student-centered learning: Demystifying the myth. *Studies in language and language teaching*, 12: 59-70.
- Vallori, A. B. (2014). *Meaningful learning in practice*. *Journal of education and human development*, 3(4): 199-209.
- Wagner, L. N. (Ed.). (2008). *Urbanization: 21st Century Issues and Challenges*. Nova Publishers.
- Widada, W., Nugroho, K. U. Z., Sari, W. P., & Pambudi, G. A. (2019). The ability of mathematical representation through realistic mathematics learning based on ethnomathematics. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, 1318(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1318/1/012073>
- Wiest, L. R. (2001). Teaching mathematics from a multicultural perspective. *Equity and Excellence in Education*, 34(1), 16–25. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1066568010340103>
- Wilson, A. (2015). A guide to phenomenological research. *Nursing Standard (2014+)*, 29(34), 38-43. <https://doi.org/10.7748/ns.29.34.38.e8821>
- Wu, P. H., Kuo, C. Y., Wu, H. K., Jen, T. H., & Hsu, Y. S. (2018). Learning benefits of secondary school students' inquiry-related curiosity: A cross-grade comparison of the relationships among learning experiences, curiosity, engagement, and inquiry abilities. *Science Education*, 102(5): 917-950.
- Yin, R. (2014). *Case Study Research: Design and Methods* (5th ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case Study Research and Applications: Design and Methods* (6th ed.). Sage Publications.